

Table 1: Search String for Every Digital Database

Digital Database	Search String
ACM Digital Library	[[Abstract: ethic] OR [Abstract: ethics] OR [Abstract: ethical] OR [Abstract: “applied ethics”] OR [Abstract: “ethical values”] OR [Abstract: “responsible ai”] OR [Abstract: “ai ethics”]] AND [[Abstract: design] OR [Abstract: development] OR [Abstract: governance] OR [Abstract: method] OR [Abstract: framework] OR [Abstract: tool] OR [Abstract: process] OR [Abstract: implementing] OR [Abstract: implementation] OR [Abstract: practices] OR [Abstract: guidelines] OR [Abstract: principles] OR [Abstract: ‘user stories”]] AND [[Abstract: “artificial intelligence”] OR [Abstract: “machine learning”] OR [Abstract: AI] OR [Abstract: ML]] AND [Publication Date: (01/01/2021 TO *)]
IEEE Xplore	((“Abstract”:ethic OR “Abstract”:ethics OR “Abstract”:ethical OR “Abstract”:“applied ethics” OR “Abstract”:“ethical values” OR “Abstract”:“responsible ai” OR “Abstract”:“ai ethics”) AND (“Abstract”:design OR “Abstract”:development OR “Abstract”:governance OR “Abstract”:method OR “Abstract”:framework OR “Abstract”:tool OR “Abstract”:process OR “Abstract”:implementing OR “Abstract”:implementation OR “Abstract”:practices OR “Abstract”:guidelines OR “Abstract”:principles OR “Abstract”: “user stories”) AND (“Abstract”:“artificial intelligence” OR “Abstract”:“machine learning” OR “Abstract”:AI OR “Abstract”:ML))
DBLP	(“ethic” OR “ethics” OR “ethical” OR “ethically” OR “applied ethics” OR “ethical values” OR “responsible ai” OR “ai ethics”) AND (“design” OR “development” OR “governance” OR “method” OR “framework” OR “tool” OR “process” OR “implementing” OR “implementation” OR “practices” OR “guidelines” OR “principles” OR “user stories”) AND (“artificial intelligence” OR “machine learning” OR “AI” OR “ML”)